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Popular Culture and Gender Disparity in Mieko Kawakami's *Breasts and Eggs*

Dr Prachi Priyanka
Assistant Professor,
Sharda University, India.

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Abstract:

Contemporary female novelists in Japan explore everyday experiences of modern women with a penetrating insight and sincerity that seeks to unfold social and cultural processes by which gender discourses operate in our lives. Sociologists have explained that women's desire for hypergamy in Japan derives from the gender-unequal Japanese labour market and fare governed by such factors as women's low income, their economic deprivation, and their loss of jobs on marriage and childbirth.

Mieko Kawakami's *Breasts and Eggs* is a novel that has won Japan's most prestigious literary award, the Akutagawa Prize. In the novel, the narrator faces dilemmas that are timely in Japan but also speak to a global audience. The novel paints a convincing image of contemporary womanhood in Japan by depicting quotidian life as lived by several women. The novel deals with larger issues such as women's oppression, precarity, domestic violence, reproductive ethics, and justice and technology. This paper intends to discuss modernist approaches in the novel and seeks to understand feminist concerns that are raised in the text with prominent narrative focus on women's bodies.

Keywords: gender, Mieko Kawakami, patriarchy, feminism, Japanese literature in Translation.

In her 1974 essay *Onnagirai* (“Woman-Hating”), Takahashi Takako offers what appears to be a scathing critique of womanhood itself—perhaps a reflection of the internal conflict and ambiguity surrounding female identity in Japanese society. The 1960s saw a wave of Japanese women writers who began to openly challenge the dominant “good wife, wise mother” (*ryōsai kenbo*) ideal—a rigid construct of femininity that many found oppressive and stifling. Through their narratives, these writers dismantled normative expectations by creating female characters who subverted traditional roles: they were unapologetically poor wives, worse mothers, and often depicted as wilfully selfish, sexually unrestrained, and openly sceptical of conventional ideals of love, marriage, and motherhood (Bullock 2010, 22). This literary rebellion coincided with a broader societal transition. The postwar years, marked by constitutional reforms that guaranteed gender equality, began to unravel older models of femininity. Although women were still burdened mainly with domestic responsibilities—freeing men to rebuild the economy—the tide was slowly shifting. Industrialisation and technological advancements in household work reduced domestic labour, drawing many women into the workforce and granting new avenues for economic independence. Long before these changes fully took hold, educated and socially conscious women at the end of the 19th century had begun protesting exploitative labour conditions and the rampant sex trade. Early feminists and socialists like Yamakawa Kikue emerged as voices against deep-rooted gender inequalities, laying the groundwork for the generations of resistance to follow. Yamakawa saw marriage as an obsolete institution:

It is a habit, a pledge between a husband and wife that a woman will submit unconditionally. In most cases, women flatter men and repress their own egos. Only when everything they do, from work to hobbies, benefits their husbands are they considered suitable companions and thus qualify as good wives (21).

Marxist literary and social critic Hirabayashi Hatsunosuke also argued that:

Inequality between men and women is not a result of inferior biological differences – rather, it is a gradual process that begins at birth because of our social system and ingrained customs. ... In today’s society women and workers comprise a class of slaves, both of whom are miserably oppressed (22).

The decline of patriarchal dominance during the 1920s ushered in a period of tentative liberation for women in Japan. As traditional authority figures struggled to maintain relevance in a rapidly changing society, their unquestioned control over women began to erode. The interwar years, marked by industrial growth and technological progress, catalysed profound social transformations that redefined the image of women in Japanese culture. Mass media, consumer markets, and cinema popularized a vibrant and varied portrait of the “modern woman”—fluid, multifaceted, and ever-evolving. While these cultural depictions occasionally reinforced traditional gender roles in postwar society, simultaneously they offered avenues for women to imagine life beyond domestic confines. These shifting representations disrupted the persistent stereotype of the docile, homebound Japanese woman, instead introducing eroticized and unconventional female figures into the urban workforce. However, many jobs available to women—such as shop assistants, waitresses, or elevator attendants—were often valued more for their aesthetic or sexual appeal than for skill, highlighting a commodified view of femininity. While lower-income women typically worked to support their families, educated women often viewed employment as a means of personal development or preparation for marriage rather than purely economic necessity. Inone Kiyoshi’s *A History of Japanese Women* (1948) framed female suppression within the context of the emperor system and positioned women’s liberation as emerging only after the emperor’s symbolic reduction following Japan’s defeat in . However, such early postwar narratives focused narrowly on elite women—bureaucrats, intellectuals, and those within state-sanctioned history. It wasn’t until the 1970s that historian Murakami Nobuhiko offered a new

lens, shifting the focus to the everyday lives of ordinary women. He argued for a perspective that considered women as an autonomous social group, operating with rhythms and realities independent of the state's framework.

Women's labour in Japan has long been marginalized, largely due to the enduring dominance of domestic ideology that shaped much of the 20th century and continues to exert influence today (Hunter 3). Early feminist historians and writers like Takamure, Sanpei, and Shimazu made groundbreaking contributions, yet their work struggled to inspire a sustained scholarly legacy. Although overtly political forms of radical feminism did not emerge in postwar Japan until the 1970s women's liberation movement, women fiction writers had already begun challenging normative gender discourses by the 1960s. This decade witnessed a surge in literary output by women, whose bold and often unsettling depictions of feminine subjectivity sparked new conversations around gender and social precarity within Japanese literary circles. These authors laid important theoretical foundations that would inform the explicitly political feminist thought of the following decade.

Japanese women's writing gained momentum following the Naturalism movement, which had earlier positioned male writers as vocational professionals. This development inadvertently opened space for women to assert a literary voice, often centered on domesticity, childbirth, and family life. However, a significant shift occurred post-2006, as women writers increasingly addressed bodily experiences, linking the female body to broader social and material realities. Contemporary Japanese feminist discourse has thus expanded to include issues such as illness, poverty, and identity crises.

Mieko Kawakami's *Breasts and Eggs* (2019), originally published as *Chichi to Ran* in 2008 and later translated into English by Sam Bett and David Boyd, stands as a powerful exploration of working-class women's everyday struggles and bodily autonomy. Kawakami interrogates

the female body through the lenses of puberty, cosmetic surgery, skin tone, stigma, and illness, crafting a narrative that bridges personal experiences with systemic critique. The novella's initial focus on the intimate, internal challenges of womanhood is expanded in the full-length English version, primarily through the protagonist Natsuko's contemplation of motherhood and bodily agency.

Set in Tokyo, the story unfolds through the perspective of thirty-year-old Natsuko, whose life intersects with those of her older sister Makiko and niece Midoriko. Through these three working-class women, Kawakami offers a deeply layered account of gendered expectations, ageing, and beauty norms in contemporary Japan. The novel critiques how the female body is inscribed within economic and sociopolitical frameworks of control, particularly under Japan's neoliberal bio-politics. This paper examines the conflicts embodied by Kawakami's characters, analyzing how their experiences reflect broader systems of gendered oppression. Focusing on themes of ageing, sexuality, and identity, it explores how *Breasts and Eggs* positions the female body as a contested site—a medium through which resistance to hegemonic narratives can be articulated.

Mieko Kawakami's *Breasts and Eggs* vividly illustrates how poverty, limited resources, and gender inequality deeply affect the lives of women. As the *International Glossary on Poverty* affirms, "poverty is inextricably linked to inequality of women" (Spicker), a premise Kawakami explores through intimate depictions of everyday struggles. A particularly poignant moment arises when the protagonist, Natsuko, reflects on a malnourished ten-year-old girl, realizing that despite a generational gap of over twenty years, the structural realities of poverty for women remain unchanged. She observes, "The kid was way too skinny. Her dark skin made the patches of psoriasis even harder to overlook... she reminded me of myself as a kid... it got me thinking about what it means to be poor" (Kawakami, 12). Kawakami further conveys economic hardship through symbolic imagery, noting that "the number of windows says it all...

if they had none, or maybe one or two, that's all you need to know" (Kawakami, 11)—a reference to Natsuko's impoverished upbringing.

The novel also underscores gender disparity through the lives of single mothers who suffer silently, particularly those afflicted by lung cancer, including Natsuko's friend Sengawa, her mother, and grandmother. These women, committed to sustaining their families after being abandoned by male figures, often ignored their deteriorating health in the process. Natsuko's mother, for example, resorted to working in a bar and engaged in extramarital relationships to feed her children after their father's departure, highlighting both the burden of survival and the absence of male responsibility.

Kawakami's narrative aligns with Vasintha Veeran's analysis in her article *Feminization of Poverty*, where she draws on Frances Fox Piven's framework: "In both industrialized and developing countries, the relationship between gender and economic stratification is evident" (Piven, 2000). Veeran's interpretation is key to understanding the link between feminism and economic struggle. Historically, women's labour was undervalued due to perceptions of physical inferiority, reproductive roles, and limited access to education and employment. However, with the emergence of feminist discourse, women began challenging these deeply entrenched societal codes. *Breasts and Eggs* powerfully contributes to this dialogue, exposing the intersection of gender, class, and embodiment as a matrix of oppression—and resistance.

The state authorities of Japan promoted healthy bodies intending to replace the image of Japan as "unclean", both materially and morally, because of the war. It served the dominant conservative stance that predicated amnesia and acritical forgetfulness of the past, for a healthy body is free from past imperfections (Igarashi 199). Besides, the government also strived to project an image of Japan as economically prosperous country whose wealth was distributed among a seemingly homogenous middleclass. Munoz observes:

While Japan achieved to overcome the aftermath of the war and generally raise the average income of many of its citizens during the decades prior to the bursting of the bubble in the early 1990s it did so by maintaining and reproducing unequal structures that would make it harder to recover once the market crashed (164).

As a consequence, women, ethnic minorities and younger generations in Japan suffer since the turn of the century from the system that had oppressed and subjugated them. Contemporary cultural studies places key focus on body studies and examines how it becomes an exciting area of theorization within philosophy, culture and literature. Shalini and Aruna argue that in the context of body, there exists a void difference between western culture and East Asian culture.

In western society women have overcome their cultural and social barriers with the aid of education. East Asian women have overcome their cultural and social barriers with the aid of education. East Asian women suffer and fight for their rights due to poverty and prevailing social conditions. The constructions of women's bodies are done through representation and discourses produced by a particular class of society (Shalini & Aruna, 22).

In East Asian countries, emphasis is made on feminine beauty. The concept of beauty is so deep-rooted in culture that many women undergo various surgeries to maintain their appearance and fit into the ideals of beauty. Women tend to see themselves through the eyes of men "as a blank page in need of inscription by the male pen, which itself has been represented as a metaphorical Penis (Gubar, 77).

According to Dumas, anti-ageing discourse is dominated by two principal streams: the refusal to *look* old and the refusal to *be* old. The former emphasizes aesthetic maintenance through practices such as cosmetic surgery, skincare products, and performance-enhancing drugs, at

the same time, the latter involves biomedical interventions aimed at extending life and delaying biological ageing (Dumas 379). These practices reflect deeper social hierarchies, as the way individuals relate to their bodies is shaped by underlying power dynamics embedded within societal structures (Bourdieu 2001). Feminist scholars have long argued that consumer culture, mass media, and the fashion-beauty complex actively reinforce these anti-ageing norms, particularly through the idealization of youth, thereby diminishing the perceived social value of women as they age.

Kawakami's *Breasts and Eggs* offers a compelling exploration of this phenomenon through the character of Makiko, whose ageing body becomes a site of anxiety and economic vulnerability. Employed in a physically demanding, low-paying, and precarious job, Makiko feels mounting pressure to conform to beauty standards in order to remain employable. Her consideration of breast augmentation reflects both a desperate attempt to hold onto her job and a deeper internalization of the societal mandate to remain youthful. This tension is vividly portrayed in a scene at the public bathhouse, where Makiko removes her towel and seeks her sister Natsuko's opinion about the shape and colour of her breasts. Natsuko's description—likening them to “mosquito bites,” “a couple of Oreos,” and “flat as pancakes,” with nipples resembling “two control knobs stuck onto her chest”—highlights the objectifying gaze that even women may direct at each other under the influence of beauty-centric ideology.

Through Makiko's body-related insecurities and her desire for bodily enhancement, Kawakami critiques the cultural narrative that conflates a woman's worth with her physical appearance, particularly her youthfulness. The novel thus reveals how anti-ageing discourse, intersecting with gender and labour precarity, exerts oppressive control over women's lives and bodies.

Giving a detailed description of her sister's nipples, Natsuko says:

And the colour. Imagine the softest pencil you could find—I guess that would be a 10B. Now imagine really bearing down with it and blacking out two little circles. These nipples were that dark. Darker than you’re thinking—all questions of physical attractiveness aside, I thought that they could stand to be a little lighter (43)

Natsuko would have told her sister that she found her nipples to be “strong” – which though a compliment from her end, would not have been taken in true spirit. Kawakami describes her opinion on women’s nipples through the protagonist Natsuko and her body concepts as she explains it as:

But what’s wrong with having strong nipples? Or dark nipples, for that matter? Who wants their nipples to be cute or pretty? You’d think that, in the world of nipples, it’d be the strong, dark, big ones that would reign supreme. Maybe someday they’ll have their moment. But probably not. (44)

In *Breasts and Eggs*, Kawakami critically engages with the cultural fixation on the female body, particularly in terms of colour and shape—attributes traditionally associated with femininity. Natsuko challenges this notion by asserting that a woman’s value should not be determined by her appearance but by her inner strength and autonomy. She rejects the dominant cultural narrative that equates femininity with traits such as cuteness, tenderness, and beauty—qualities often imagined through a male gaze. The idealized feminine body is socially constructed to conform to narrow descriptors: delicate features, slender necks, curvaceous hips, and even racialized markers like blonde hair. These expectations are not inherent but shaped by historically patriarchal vocabularies that define what it means to be “feminine.”

Makiko, a single mother with limited education and economic mobility, internalizes these societal pressures. Her desperation to remain viable in a job that relies heavily on physical presentation leads her to consider breast augmentation: “I have been thinking about getting breast implants” (Kawakami 37). Her body becomes her only capital in a system that places

value on women based on appearance rather than ability. In a striking moment of existential frustration, she cries out: “There’s no such thing as women... there are no men no women and nothing else” (Kawakami 64). This declaration underscores her yearning for a post-gender society, one that does not subject individuals to rigid binary identities or tie their worth to visual appeal.

Kawakami thus critiques the commodification of the female body and the socio-economic constraints that force women like Makiko to navigate survival through bodily compliance. The novel exposes how these entrenched gender norms limit women's agency and perpetuate a culture in which physical appearance is mistaken for personal value.

Though Makiko knows the pain behind breast implants, she forces herself to take such risks because she works as a hostess in a bar. Juliana Buritica Alzate writes:

Makiko emphasises the different places and research she did while making her decision, and it is precisely the wide variety of offer s that reinforce the notion of an ideal, perfect type of body that should be, and can be pursued. Hence, cosmetic surgery can be viewed as a service – that “cuts,” hurts, and heals – offered by an industry that merges health and beauty discourses, a by-product of current consumer-driven, neoliberal societies. (2020, 536)

Michel Thévoz’s assertion that “there is no body but the painted body” (1984:7) underscores the idea that the human body is never a neutral entity—it is always marked by cultural, social, and symbolic meanings. In this framework, the body functions as a site of inscription, essential for social recognition and exchange. This becomes particularly evident in contemporary society, where women’s bodies are subject to intense scrutiny and are disproportionately evaluated according to aesthetic norms. As noted in the introduction, the American Society for Aesthetic Plastic Surgery (ASAPS 2010) reports that women comprise ninety percent of all

cosmetic procedures, with breast augmentation, liposuction, eyelid surgery, and anti-wrinkle injections ranking among the most common treatments associated with ageing.

This overwhelming gender disparity reveals how deeply entrenched societal expectations of female beauty are. Western culture continues to associate a woman's social worth with her adherence to youth-centric beauty standards (Bartley 1990; Bordo 1993). Numerous studies have shown that women are far more susceptible than men to the evaluative gaze, internalizing cultural expectations that link ageing with loss of value (Featherstone & Wernick 1995). Susan Sontag (1978) famously identified a "double standard of ageing," wherein women suffer greater social penalties than men as they grow older, particularly through "sexual disqualification" (Sontag 73). As appearance often dictates how women are treated in both personal and professional contexts, beauty becomes a form of social currency (Brown & Jasper 2000).

Feminist theorist Susan Bordo argues that this pressure fosters a culture in which women's bodies are continuously subjected to external control and transformation. In striving to meet an idealized feminine image, women's bodies are "habituated to external regulation, subjection, transformation, [and] improvement" (Bordo 166). Feminist scholarship continues to emphasize that the body is central to a woman's lived experiences, shaping not only identity but also access to power, agency, and autonomy in society. De Mello raises a concern here:

Whether it's because women must constantly monitor their appearance and behaviors in order to please men, under whose gaze they continuously operate, or whether it's because they must take into account the ways in which their reproductive abilities influence the activities that they engage in, women are always aware of their bodies in ways that men are not (17).

A clock not only mirrors the phases of the day, but also has “a poetic effect that tries to organize and give meaning to the cycles and evolutionary processes experienced by each of us at different points in our life” (172). Simultaneously, it can also transfer the productive pressures of achieving certain goals within a limited time span. The clock becomes through this association not only a physical but also a mental mechanism of control that fuse productive and reproductive lives. Martina Yopo Diaz (2021) points out how this effect is particularly significant in governing the lives of women by the narrative of ‘biological clock’ that is perceived to impact reproduction, child bearing and conciliation. It is this struggle for acceptance, resistance, or adaptation against gender conventions and expectations that is exposed in Kawakami's *Breasts and Eggs*.

The first part of the novel engages with Midoriko's curiosity and lack of sexual awareness that is exemplified by her journal entry about how she has recently learned that women bodies have “ova”, which literally means egg. Further, she innocently ponders over inequality in gender narration: “How is it possible I knew about sperm first? That doesn't seem fair” (Kawakami 14). Midoriko's remark reminds us of the absence of female writing about body and gender even in academic books – a kind of inequality in society where women have restrictive knowledge of their own bodies. The journal entries of Midoriko gives us a glimpse into the turmoil and frustrations of an adolescent girl confused over the changing contours of her own body. She writes:

My hands move. My feet move. I don't know how to move them, though. It's like everything is moving all these parts. It's funny. It's like I'm in there, somewhere inside myself, and the body I'm in keeps on changing, more and more and more and more, in ways I don't even know (50).

Like her mother and aunt, Midoriko too has her own set of struggles that she jots down in her journal. Her mother's obsession with breast implants infuriates her at times – but she also understands her sacrifices and the economic limitations. She is puzzled and outraged at the physiological changes she witnesses in her body – concerning menstruation, sex and the idea of fertility as linked to femininity and motherhood:

It feels like I'm trapped inside my body. It decides when I get hungry, and when I'll get my period. From birth to death, you have to keep eating and making money just to stay alive. I see what working every night does to my mom. It takes it out of her. But what's it all for? Life is hard enough with just one body. Why would anyone ever want to make another one? (Kawakami 49)

Her mother's obsession to get breast enhancements upsets her all the more and she enters:

I stand nearby to listen. I hear everything. Ever since I had my daughter, she says ... It's always the same line about breastfeeding me. Idiot, so you want your body to be the way you used to be? Then why'd you even have me? (113)

Midoriko raises some pertinent questions through these entries and when she actually confronts her mother in Natsuko's apartment – the friction between the mother and daughter implicitly tackles a significant issue of feminism: that one woman's femininity and freedom should not come at the expense of another's (Foster) Breasts and body image are a concern even for Natsuko - though unlike her sister, she learns to accept it. She recalls:

I remember what it felt like when my breasts started getting bigger. How out of nowhere I had grown these things. It was incredible how much they hurt back then if anything bumped into them. As a kid, whenever I saw the naked women in the magazines that the kids in the neighbourhood got their hands on, or saw a grownup woman expose her

body on TV, I guess on some level I thought that someday all those parts of me would fill out, too, and I would have a body just like them. Except that never happened.

The gap between real and imagined female bodies are brought out through the painful discovery that the two things were unrelated. The desire to fit into the standards set by male gaze where a female body is “pretty”, “sexy” and “provokes sexual fantasy” makes real women not “value” the kind of body they have. By writing about the female body that does not fit into the mould of typical standards of beauty – Kawakami gives voice to many women who struggle with the futile tags and objectification of female bodies.

The second part of *Breasts and Eggs* shifts focus to Natsuko's internal struggle as she navigates the uncertainties of motherhood outside conventional frameworks. Despite her ability to form meaningful human connections, Natsuko remains detached from sexual desire—an emotional dissonance that prompts her to consider non-traditional paths to becoming a mother. Through Natsuko's journey, Kawakami exposes the hidden and often precarious world of sperm donation in Japan, revealing a system fraught with legal ambiguities, ethical dilemmas, and social taboos. The novel delves into the emotional and financial challenges associated with fertility treatments and highlights the broader issue of how reproductive health has been privatized and commodified. Natsuko's conflicted feelings—her lack of sexual interest yet longing for motherhood—are further complicated by her own traumatic upbringing in a household devoid of paternal stability. Raised by a mother and grandmother after her father's abandonment, Natsuko's reflections force her to confront the institution of the family itself, questioning whether her desire to have a child, stems from genuine autonomy or internalized social expectations. She wrestles with multiple thoughts which go against the prescriptive means of gender identification:

‘If you think about it,’ I said, ‘that’s what it was like when we were younger. Sex wasn’t a thing, it had no real role in our lives, yo u know? It didn’t matter if you were a woman or not. It’s just, for me, things stayed that way. It’s like that part of me never grew up. I don’t think there’s anything strange or unusual about it, though. That’s why sometimes I have to ask myself: Am I really a woman? Like I said, I have the body of a woman, I know that. But do I have the mind of a woman? Do I feel like a woman? I can’t say either way with any confidence. I mean, what does feeling like a woman actually entail? I’m not sure how that relates to how I feel about sex, but it must.’ (Kawakami 440)

In an interview, Kawakami said she never intended the novel to be feminist. She was just writing about human experience and it was only natural to talk about women. The book expands on the idea of reproductive ethics from the narrow hegemonic debate on pro-choice/ pro-life to include the dignity of women and problematizing the bio-essential maternal instinct and present alternatives available to women in Japan who break away from the norm. When Natsuko meets a sperm donor Yuriko, he tells her an allegory that sees motherhood and act of bringing life to the world from a completely fresh and surprising perspective: The allegory brings to question the reproductive ethics and act of bringing life when we know that one of the ten kids does not want to “wake up” to a painful life. Yuriko says: “If you bring a new life into the world, that’s exactly what you’re doing. You are waking one of these kids up. You know what makes you think doing that is okay? Because it’s got nothing to do with you. ... Because whoever the child is, the one who lives and dies consumed with pain, could never be you” (285). The philosophical note here gives an entry point to discuss guilt, pressure, and motherhood as a selfish act.

Gender disparity in Japanese popular culture and ideology has often been analyzed through the lens of broad systemic structures; however, it is equally important to consider the profoundly personal and embodied impacts of these inequalities. This chapter has examined how

representations of the body in *Breasts and Eggs* lay bare the interwoven systems of economic and gendered oppression, highlighting the nuanced and often invisible forms of violence that shape women's lives. Kawakami's novel presents a spectrum of female experiences—across class, age, and desire—through characters who perceive the world differently based on their lived realities. Makiko's fixation on breast augmentation as a means of survival, Midoriko's adolescent confrontation with womanhood, and Natsuko's ambivalence toward sex and unconventional approach to motherhood collectively challenge normative discourses on femininity, labour, and family. *Breasts and Eggs* thus contributes to an emerging literary and feminist discourse that calls for broader inclusion, intersectional awareness, and redefinition of gender roles. While literary representation plays a critical role in validating these shifts, continued interdisciplinary research is essential to trace and sustain the momentum of these evolving narratives.

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